

Supplementary Information for

Integrating chemo- and bioinformatics with *in vitro* biological assays to discover potential ACE2 and Mpro inhibitors against SARS-CoV-2

Ryan S. Ramos ^{a,b,*}, João S. N. de Souza ^c, Mariana H. Chaves ^c, Joaquín M. Campos^d, Willyenne M. Dantas ^{e,f}, Lindomar J. Pena ^f, Maracy L. D. S. Andrade^b, Cleydson B. R. Santos ^{a,b,c*}

- ^a Graduate Program in Biotechnology and Biodiversity-Network BIONORTE, Federal University of Amapá, Macapá, 68903-419 Amapá, Brazil; ryanquimico@hotmail.com (R.S.R)
 - ^b Laboratory of Modeling and Computational Chemistry, Department of Biological and Health Sciences, Federal University of Amapá, 68902-280 Macapá, AP, Brazil;
 - ^c Chemistry Department, Federal University of Piauí, Campus Universitário Ministro Petrônio Portela, Av. Nossa Senhora de Fátima, Bairro Ininga, CEP: 64.049-550, Teresina, PI, Brazil; sammynery@ufpi.edu.br (J.S.NS.); mariana@ufpi.edu.br (M.H.C.)
 - ^d Department of Pharmaceutical and Organic Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Campus of Cartuja, University of Granada, 18071 Granada, Spain;
 - ^e Department of Chemistry, Federal Rural University of Pernambuco, Recife 52171-900, Brazil; willyenne.dantas@ufrpe.br (W.M.D.);
 - ^f Department of Virology, Aggeu Magalhães Institute (IAM), Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz), Recife 50670-420, Brazil; lindomar.pena@fiocruz.br (L.J.P.);
- * Correspondence: breno@unifap.br (C.B.R.S)

Table of Contents

1. Supplementary figures	S1
--------------------------	----

1. Supplementary figures

Figure S1. RMSD representation of the crystallographic ligand (green) and best docking pose (cyan) in the 11b.